

“Evaluation of Processing Induced Morphology and Its Relation to Mechanical Fracture Behavior of ESBR and SSBR”

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Summary

- Introduce the problem
- Evidence of microdomains in ESBR & SSBR
- Synthesis & postsynthesis induced interfaces improve processability
- Processing induced mixing zones analogous to flaws for crack propagation.
- Examples: Role interfaces play in wear
- Conclusions

Reasons for Gel Formation

- Chemical crosslinking
- Physical entanglements
- Branching at high conversion
- Post synthesis processing
 - Rapid, nonequilibrium colloidal destabilization (in ESR, Baker 1949)
 - Slow relaxation in entangled chain (Greassley 1980)
 - Crosslinking during storage and mixing (Cooper & Bahary 1961)
 - Long branching is detrimental to processability (Nakajima 1979)

The Problem

Neat elastomers are considered to be

- Continuum-amorphous
- Entangled Networks
- Crosslinking and branching

Interfaces may form during

- Synthesis “emulsion polymerization”
 - Microgel or macrogel
- Post- synthesis processing
 - Masticated Shear Striae
 - Secondary crosslinking

Emulsion Particle ESBR

AFM for Solid ESBR

Flatten

- Two-dimensional illustration of
- (a) Latex particle
 - (b) Microgel (microdomain)
 - (c) Interdomain bridging chains

TEM For Solid Rubbers

Complete deformation at
shear rate 1040 s^{-1}

ESBR

SSBR

NR

Cast-Film Subemulsion Domains

ESBR

SSBR

NR

Shear Stress-Strain Behavior of Neat Polymers

Properties	ESBR	SSBR
Styrene %	23.5	23
Vinyl 1, 2 %	17	11
Cis 1, 4 %	18	35
Trans 1, 4 %	65	54
T _g (°C)	-55	-70
M _n × 10 ⁻⁶	12	11

Effects of mastication numbers on apparent shear stress and shear rate.

Effects of Mastication on Gel and MWD

Example:

No Gel -if filter size is 300 μm ASTM 3616-86 -

10-17 % -if GPC standard filter of pore size 0.45 μm is used.

Effects on Die Swell

Effects of mastication on the die swell properties of pure SSBR, ESBR and NR samples.

Mixing Zones and Microdomains

SSBR

x5.0k 0096 15KV 10µm

x5.0k 0093 15KV 10µm

ESBR

Mixing Zones and Microdomains

SSBR

— 1 μm

ESBR

Controlled Mixing Zones

Directional Mixing Zones Formation in Filled ESBR

BMZ = 0.5-1 μm

Compression direction \uparrow

Crack Branching in Gum Rubber

Direction
of precut

Direction
of mixing
zones

Crack Banching in Filled Rubber

Direction
of mixing
zones

Direction
of precut

Wear Machine

1 μm

Abraded Surfaces of Gum ESBR

Effects of processing anisotropy of gum SSBR on initial slip over a Mylar belt. The surfaces represent damage formation from (a) parallel and (b) perpendicular arrangement of belt and mixing zone directions. belt direction and mill direction. ——— ↑

Abraded Surface of Gum SSBR

Belt slip direction and
mixing zones direction

Effects of processing anisotropy of gum SSBR on initial slip over a Mylar belt. The surfaces represent damage formation from (a) parallel and (b) perpendicular arrangement of belt and mixing zone directions.

Wear Ridges Formation

Example of Role of Interfaces in Wear

ESBR

SSBR

Wear Process & Rubber Components in ESBR

1-Microdomain

2-Macrogel (secondary rubber particle)

3-Filled rubber aggregate

Wear process & Rubber Components in SSBR

Surface Flaws and Crack Propagation

SSBR

Conclusions

- Found the presence of microdomains of high-density gels formed from physical and chemical entanglements during polymerization.
- Sub-emulsion particles created during emulsion polymerization remain intact during the processing steps commonly used in the fabrication of rubber articles.
- Processing induced morphologies are found for ESR and SSR properties.
- Grain-like structures from the polymerization and processing induced mixing zone structures play a role in fracture and wear processes.

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